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RESEARCH ARTICLE

LAND MANAGEMENT PRACTICES ADOPTION AND FARM PRODUCTIVITY: AN EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS OF THE ADOPTION BARRIERS AMONG THE NIGERIAN FARMER

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ABSTRACT

In Nigeria, agricultural land is increasingly threatened by soil degradation, nutrient depletion, erosion, and unsustainable cultivation practices. Although sustainable land management practices (SLMP) have been proven to improve soil quality and increase agricultural productivity, adoption rates among farmers in Nigeria are still markedly low. The study therefore identified and analysed the influence of land management practices adoption on farm productivity and the associated constraints to effective SLMP adoption in Oyo state, Nigeria. Using a multistage sampling technique to group the entire population of registered villages in Oyo and Saki Agricultural zone, a total of 278 farmers were randomly selected using proportionate probability sample approach. Collected data were analysed using descriptive and regression analysis. Results of the descriptive analysis revealed that crop rotation and intercropping were the most commonly practiced land management method among farmers, while the most pressing challenge reported by farmers was financial constraints and poor road networks. The regression results also revealed a positive and significant influence of crop rotation, and strip cropping on farm productivity ($p < 0.01$). The study recommends the urgent need for rural infrastructure development, particularly feeder roads, to ease farm access, reduces transaction costs, and improves market linkages.

KEYWORDS

Productivity, Land Management Practices, Crop Rotation, Sustainable Land Management Practices

Introduction

Land is one of the most essential natural resources for agricultural production, rural livelihoods, and economic development. In many developing countries, especially in Nigeria, agricultural land is increasingly threatened by soil degradation, nutrient depletion, erosion, and unsustainable cultivation practices (Lal, 2015; Nkonya *et al.*, 2016). These challenges have contributed to declining agricultural productivity despite rising food demand and population pressure. As a response, sustainable

land management practices (SLMPs) have been promoted as strategic interventions to maintain soil fertility, conserve natural resources, and enhance long-term agricultural output (Branca, McCarthy, Lipper, & Jolejole, 2011).

SLMPs encompass a wide range of agronomic and conservation strategies such as crop rotation, minimum tillage, mulching, manure application, cover cropping, agro-forestry, and various soil and water

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conservation techniques. Empirical evidence demonstrates that these practices can significantly improve soil structure, enhance water retention, reduce erosion, and increase crop productivity (Kassie *et al.*, 2015). Studies from sub-Saharan Africa have shown that farmers who adopt integrated soil fertility management and conservation agriculture practices tend to achieve higher yields and improved resilience to climatic shocks compared to non-adopters (Twomlow *et al.*, 2008; Marenya & Barrett, 2007).

Despite these benefits, the adoption of SLMPs remains considerably low in many rural settings of Nigeria. Adoption behaviour is shaped by multiple socio-economic and institutional factors, including limited access to information, inadequate extension services, insecure land tenure, high labour requirements, credit constraints, and farmers' perceptions of the cost-benefit trade-offs associated with long-term land investments (Kassie *et al.*, 2015). Furthermore, variations in agro-ecological conditions influence how effectively land management practices translate into productivity gains, indicating that outcomes are not uniform across contexts (Giller *et al.*, 2011).

Given this complexity, there is a growing interest in empirical studies that assess not only the productivity effects of SLMPs but also the barriers that inhibit their adoption. Understanding these dynamics is critical for designing targeted agricultural policies, improving extension service delivery, and enhancing the sustainability of production systems. Therefore, this study seeks to identify and analyse the influence of land management practices adoption on farm productivity and identify the key constraints that limit their adoption among the Nigerian farmers.

Statement of the Research Problem

Agricultural productivity in Nigeria remains below its potential despite the availability of improved practices capable of reversing soil degradation and enhancing crop performance. Persistent challenges such as soil nutrient depletion, erosion, declining soil organic matter, and land fragmentation continue to undermine farm output and threaten food security (Lal, 2015; Nkonya *et al.*, 2016). Although sustainable land management practices have been shown to improve soil quality and increase agricultural productivity, adoption rates among farmers in Nigeria are still markedly low (Kassie *et al.*, 2015).

The limited adoption of SLMPs is often attributed to a combination of economic, institutional, and knowledge-related barriers. Smallholder farmers frequently lack access to extension services, credit facilities, and technical inputs required to implement these practices effectively. Furthermore, empirical evidence on the magnitude of productivity gains associated with SLMPs is mixed and context-specific (Giller *et al.*, 2011). This highlights a critical gap in understanding how different land management practices perform under varying socio-economic and agro-ecological conditions in Nigeria. Without such context-sensitive evidence, policymakers and development practitioners may be unable to design effective interventions to promote widespread adoption.

Therefore, the central problem this study seeks to address is the limited empirical understanding of land management practices adoption among the Nigerian farmers and the main constraints inhibiting farmers' adoption of these practices in Nigeria.

Objectives of the Study

1. The objectives of the study were to:
2. identify land management practices adopted by the farmers in Oyo State, Nigeria.
3. identify the key constraints inhibiting farmers' adoption of land management practices in Oyo State, Nigeria.

Hypothesis of the study

H₀₁: Land management practices Adoption does not significantly influence farm's productivity in Oyo State, Nigeria.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Concepts of Land Management

Land management is the techniques used in preserving soil fertility and increase crop yields. It encompasses all actions related to the economic and environmental management of land as a resource. It includes soil amendment techniques, which include both historic and contemporary land conservation techniques. In order to improve soil nutrient components, both traditional and contemporary land management techniques must be sufficiently applied during farm operations, depending on the cropping patterns selected by the farmer (Agboola *et al.*, 2015). According to Desta *et al.*, (2021), farmers suggest land management strategies that combine agronomic and engineering techniques to increase agricultural productivity, particularly in marginal soils.

Land management techniques are used for sustainable crop production, such as agro-forestry, shifting cultivation, ridge across slopes, crop rotation, cover cropping, manure application, mulching, fertilizer application, irrigation, bush burning, and planting trees to intercept wind. The native soil fertility level and land management techniques have a significant impact on agricultural productivity. Given that land is the productive foundation of Nigerian agriculture and the source of income for many rural and urban livelihoods, the management issue can be taken for granted (Oluwatayo *et al.*, 2019).

Concept of Sustainable Land Management

Sustainable Land Management (SLM) is a knowledge-based process that integrates land, water, biodiversity, and environmental management (including input and output externalities) (Okereke & Alimba, 2024). This relates to making sure that land use choices are environmentally sound, socially just, and economically feasible (Adisa, *et al.*, 2024; Odii, Amoge, & Ejiofor, 2024). The technologies and their embodied techniques that are used to guarantee that the objectives of sustainable land management are achieved in any particular agro-ecosystem are then referred to as sustainable land management practices (Fasolo, 2024; Odii, *et al.*, 2024). According to the World Bank, (2006), sustainable land management is a process that balances the need to protect the environment with the need to ensure ecosystem services.

Principles of Sustainable Land Management

Rockstrom, *et al.*, (2013) identified a set of criteria for rain-fed systems of sustainable land management. He affirmed that effective land management necessitates an integrated and synergistic

approach to resource management that incorporates locally suitable combinations of the following technological options:

Buildup surface mulch, enriched fallows, agro-forestry, cover crops, and crop residue management;

Integrate plant nutrition management with locally appropriate and cost-effective combinations of organic or inorganic and on-farm or off-farm sources of plant nutrients (such as use of organic manures, crop residues, and rhizobial nitrogen fixation; transfer of nutrients released by weathering in the deeper soil layers to the surface by way of tree roots and leaf litter; and use of rock phosphate, lime, and mineral fertilizer).

Better crop management using improved seeds of appropriated varieties; improved crop establishment at the beginning of the rains (to increase protective ground cover, thereby reducing water loss and soil erosion); effective weed control; and integrated pest management;

Better rainwater management to increase infiltration and eliminate or reduce runoff so as to improve soil moisture conditions within the rooting zone, thereby lessening the risk of moisture stress during dry spells, while reducing erosion.

Concept of Productivity

Productivity measurement is the quantification of both the output and input resources of a productive system. The intent is to come up with a quantified monitoring index. The goal of productivity measurement is productivity improvement, which involves a combination of increased effectiveness and a better use of available resources. While productivity can be given the sort of shorthand definition as the ratio between output and input, what productivity really is, as well as how it can be measured, has always provoked a great deal of controversy among experts.

In practice, however, both measurement of outputs and inputs involves the problem of aggregation; this problem alone has situated productivity measurement in the realm of complexity. For example, the question of how to aggregate different products that do not have constant quality or characteristics constitutes the veil to be removed from output measurement. In the same vein, the problem of how to aggregate the different types of inputs into a well-defined composite unit remains a critical one on the side of input measurement. To solve output and input aggregation problems, particularly when heterogeneous inputs and outputs are combined, some authors have suggested that inputs should be added up in 'constant price' money values. The same thing should be done for output (David, 1972; Iyaniwura & Osoba, 1983).

Factors Militating Against Land Management Practices Adoption

Climate change has an impact on cropping patterns and crop productivity because weather fluctuations have a detrimental effect on crop productivity due to erratic rainfall and shifting temperature patterns, which influence farmers' decisions about when to plant their crops. The World Bank, (2006) states that climate change has a variety of effects on agriculture, including variations in rainfall, average temperatures, and climate extremes that have a significant impact on soil erosion (such as floods and droughts), changes in diseases and pests, changes in carbon dioxide, changes in the nutritional value of food, changes in growing

seasons, and changes in sea level. Changes in rainfall patterns will result in more water scarcity and related crop drought issues, as well as changes to irrigation schedules.

Financial limitations are another issue that many farmers deal with since they will perform below expectations if they don't have enough money. Adoption of sustainable land management (SLM) is fraught with financial difficulties. Smallholders, who usually have narrow profit margins, frequently cannot afford the initial investment costs for technologies like better irrigation systems, soil conservation structures, or organic fertilizers (Yegbeme, *et al.*, 2018). These constraints include high input costs, a lack of credit availability (Magaji, 2004), a lack of investment capital (Okoroafor, *et al.*, 2018), and the lack of risk-reduction instruments such as crop insurance (Tanko, *et al.*, 2025). In order to increase crop output in the research area, land degradation (the loss of soil nutrients) must be addressed.

Theory of planned behavior

Theory of planned behavior (TPB) is one of the most widely used models in explaining and predicting individual behavioural intention and acceptance of technology. TPB is an attitude – intention-behaviour model, which says that an individual's behaviour is determined by perceived behavioural control and intention. An attitude, subjective norm, and perceived behavioural control, in turn determine intention (Tooraj and Sahel, 2011). The TPB proposed that an individual's intention to perform an act is affected by his attitude towards the act, subjective norms and perceived behavioural control (Ozdemir and Trott, 2009). According to theory of planned behaviour (TPB), an individual behaviour is determined by behavioural intention and perceived behavioural control, and behavioural intention is determined by attitude towards behaviour, subjective norm and perceived behaviour control. Attitudes towards behaviour reflect one's favourable or unfavourable feeling of performing behaviour. Subjective norm reflects one's perception of others relevant opinions on whether or not he or she should perform a particular behaviour. Therefore, perceived behavioural control reflects one's perception of the availability of resources or opportunities necessary to perform behaviour (Haghighinasab, 2009). In line with the above, it is observed that the difference between this theory and TRA is the addition of behavioural intention and perceived behavioural control therein. However, Kathryn, (2010) employed the behavioural approach to understand rice farmers' technology adoption decisions in Indonesia. This theory reflects the behavioural attitude of maize and soybean crop farmers in adopting land management practices.

Methodology

The study was carried out in Oyo state Nigeria, an area characterized with a tropical climatic condition. The population of the study includes maize and soybean crop farmers in Oyo and Saki Agricultural Zone of Oyo State Nigeria. Using a multistage sampling technique, respondents were selected from the list of registered villages in Oyo and Saki Agricultural zone. A total of 278 Maize and Soybean crop farmers were randomly selected from each selected Local Government areas. Collected data were analysed using descriptive and inferential statistics. Ordinary least square (OLS) regression

analysis was carried out to determine the effects of land management practices on Productivity in Oyo State, Nigeria.

RESULT, INTERPRETATION AND DISCUSSIONS

Land Management Practices Adoption among Farmers in Oyo State, Nigeria

The results presented in Table 1 revealed the extent of adoption of various practices and provide insight into the prevailing land use behavior among rural farmers in Oyo State, Nigeria. The table showed that the most commonly practiced land management method among respondents was crop rotation, reported by 37.1% of farmers. This finding is consistent with those of Ayodele, *et al.*, (2012), who emphasized that crop rotation, is widely practiced due to its benefits in maintaining soil fertility, promoting biological pest control, and reducing disease cycles. Intercropping was the second most adopted practice, with 19.1% of the respondents using this method. This finding aligned with the opinion of Adugna and Bekele, (2021) that intercropping is known to maximize land use efficiency, improve yield stability, and reduce the risk of total crop failure. Use of chemical fertilizers accounted for 17.3%, suggesting moderate reliance on inorganic inputs to boost productivity. Shifting cultivation was reported by 10.1% of respondents. Only 3.9% and 3.2% of respondents practiced mechanized plowing and minimum tillage, respectively. This suggests limited access to agricultural machinery and a low level of conservation tillage awareness. Strip cropping, practiced by 8.3% of the farmers, while contour farming was the least adopted practice at 1.1%, despite its proven benefits in controlling soil erosion on sloped lands. The low adoption rate of these practices could be attributed to a lack of technical knowledge, labor requirements, and insufficient extension services. The results demonstrate that while farmers in the study area adopt a range of land management strategies, traditional and low-input methods such as crop rotation and intercropping dominate. The limited use of conservation and mechanized practices underscores the need for policy interventions, including training, input subsidies, and mechanization support, to promote climate-smart and sustainable land management.

Table 1: Analysis of Identified Land Management Practices Adopted by the Farmers in Oyo State, Nigeria

Land management Practices Adopted	Frequency	%
Crop rotation	103	37.1
Intercropping	53	19.1
Shifting Cultivation	28	10.1
Minimum Tillage	9	3.2
Mechanized Ploughing	11	3.9
Use of Chemical	48	17.3
Contour Farming	23	8.3
Strip Cropping	3	1.1

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Constraints Inhibiting Farmers' Adoption of Land Management Practices in Oyo State, Nigeria

The results in Table 2 revealed multiple constraints that hinder the adoption of land management practices in the study area. The most pressing challenge reported by farmers was financial constraints (69.06%), and Poor Road Networks (59.71%), which aligns with recent evidence that inadequate access to credit remains a major bottleneck for agricultural innovation and sustainability in Sub-Saharan Africa (Abayomi & Yusuf, 2022). Poor Road Networks (59.71%), which limit market accessibility, increase transaction costs, and reduce the incentive for farmers to invest in improved land management practices as observed by Adeoye, *et al.*, (2021) and Olaniyi, (2023). Poor Soil Fertility and Degradation accounted for 51.80% and Weak Government Policy (50.36%) were also highlighted, reflecting the broader structural issues of declining soil health and inadequate policy frameworks to support sustainable agriculture (World Bank, 2021; Nkonya & Mirzabaev, 2022). Similarly, limited government subsidies (46.40%) and restricted availability of quality seeds and fertilizers (44.60%) further exacerbate farmers' inability to adopt improved practices, echoing findings that input accessibility and affordability remain critical determinants of technology uptake (Rahman & Chikaire, 2020; Eze, *et al.*, 2023). Additionally, climate change and weather variability (37.41%) were recognized as significant constraints, consistent with growing concerns that erratic rainfall and prolonged droughts reduce farmers' resilience and discourage long-term investments in soil conservation (Moyo & Chivenge, 2024). Other constraints included land tenure insecurity (10.07%), gender barriers (9.71%), and lack of community cooperation (5.71%), which have also been reported as underlying factors affecting farmers' capacity to sustainably manage land resources (Akinyemi, *et al.*, 2022; Agwu & Nwankwo, 2024). These findings highlight that while sustainable land management practices can enhance productivity, structural, financial, and institutional challenges remain the greatest obstacles to achieving widespread adoption by the Nigerian farmers.

Table 2: Constraints Limiting Land Management Practices Adoption in the Study Area

Constraints	%
Poor soil fertility and Degradation	51.80%
Climate change and weather variability	37.41%
High cost of mechanization and labour	17.99%
Limited knowledge and extension services	8.91%
Land tenure insecurity	10.07%
Gender barrier	9.71%
Lack of community cooperation	5.71%
Limited government subsidies	46.40%
Limited availability of quality seeds and fertilizer	44.60%
Poor road network	59.71%
Financial constraints	69.06%
Weak Government policy	50.36%

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Test of Hypothesis

H₀₁: Land Management Practices Adoption does not significantly Influence Farm's Productivity in Oyo State, Nigeria

The regression results presented in the table 3, however, provide compelling evidence to reject this null hypothesis. Several variables exhibit statistically significant effects on productivity at the 1% and 5% significance levels, indicating that land management practices adoption indeed have a measurable influence on farmers' productivity. The results revealed that land management practices such as crop rotation, shifting cultivation, and strip cropping were positively and significantly associated with productivity ($p < 0.01$, $p < 0.05$, and $p < 0.01$, respectively). These findings underscore the importance of sustainable land management practices adoption in maintaining soil fertility, enhancing moisture retention, and improving crop yields. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected, as the analysis reveals significant relationships between land management practices adoption and farmers' productivity in Oyo State, Nigeria.

Table 3: Regression Analysis Showing the Influence of Land Management Practices Adoption on Farm's Productivity in Oyo State, Nigeria

Productivity	Coef.	Std. Err.	T	P>t
Crop rotation	0.386	.075	5.12* **	0.000
Intercropping	0.051 3243	.21841 89	0.23	0.814
Shift cultivation	0.288 4566	.12067 56	2.39* *	0.018
Minimum Tillage	0.035 1279	.11637 67	-0.30	0.763
Mechanical	0.218 1887	.13674 92	-1.60	0.112
Chemical Fertilizer	0.094 0	0.073	1.29	0.197
Contour farm	0.180 8176	.11831 83	-1.53	0.128
Strip cropping	.3712 89	.12947 6	2.87* **	0.004
_Constant	1.089 921	.68332 18	1.60	0.112

***significant at 1%, **significant at 5%;

Source: Authors' computations 2025

Summary

Findings revealed the econometric results which showed that sustainable land practices like crop rotation, shifting cultivation and strip cropping, significantly affected productivity. The model explained 90.6% of the variation in farm's productivity, confirming that the adoption of effective land management practices is central to improving farm output.

Conclusion

The study revealed that among all the identified constraints to the land management practices adoption by the Nigerian farmers, financial limitations and poor road networks are the most severe. In conclusion, the study highlights that while sustainable land practices have strong potential to enhance productivity, systemic challenges, particularly financial, infrastructural, and institutional barriers, remain the most critical obstacles. Improving rural infrastructure, enhancing extension services, and implementing financial supportive measures are therefore essential for enhancing sustainable land management practices adoption and ensuring long-term agricultural productivity in Nigeria.

Recommendation

Based on the findings, the study recommends the following;

Urgent need for rural infrastructure development, particularly feeder roads, to ease farm access, reduces transaction costs, and improves market linkages.

Government should support rural financial institutions, cooperative lending schemes, and government-backed agricultural credit programs with flexible repayment options is critical to enhancing the adoption of sustainable practices

Government should promote sustainable land management practices (LMPs) among the farmers through farmer-specific extension programs, awareness campaigns, and demonstration farms will ensure soil fertility and yield improvement

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